

THE MAIN IMPORTANCE OF THE LOCAL FERTILIZER APPLICATION DEVICE BETWEEN THE ROWS OF CROPS

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Abstract: The article mainly describes the technology of fertilizing machines in row-cropped fields, that is, the types of local fertilizer application techniques and technologies, and the efficiency of machines that apply local fertilizer between rows. As a result of the research, it was found that applying local fertilizer between rows led to better plant development and positive changes in productivity, and increased humus layer of cultivated fields, leading to a 10-20% reduction in water consumption.

Keywords: Local fertilizer, bunker, gear transfers, plant, milling cutter, suspended aggregate, fertilizer discharge pipe, cotton.

Introduction. As is known, the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the countries specialized in agriculture, therefore, our state has adopted relevant legal documents for the development of agriculture in our country. In particular, in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PE-5853 dated October 23, 2019 “On approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030 [1]”, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-3712 dated May 10, 2018 “On measures to further improve the mechanisms for timely provision of agriculture with agricultural machinery” [2], a number of Decrees and Resolutions have been signed on the development of fundamental and applied research and innovative activities in the field of agricultural mechanization.

In particular, the productivity of agricultural crops and the productivity of livestock all depend on how we use the land. If we look at the extent to which soil composition has changed in irrigated areas, the average over the last 15 years is summarized as follows: the soil, especially its topsoil, has become very dense, its specific gravity is 1.8 sm^3 instead of the standard 1.2 sm^3 , or an increase of 50%. The main reasons for this are monoculture, shallow plowing of the land, the introduction of heavy machinery into the fields (especially rubber-tire machinery), insufficient provision of arable fields with organic fertilizers, and as a result, a sharp decrease in humus, which gives fertility to the soil [3]. At the same time, in European countries such as the Netherlands, Denmark, and Germany, the amount of humus in the soil is 4-4.6%, in Russia it is 3.6%, in Ukraine it is 3.2%, and in Belarus it is 2.4%, while in our Uzbekistan this figure is 1.1-1.3%. The amount of humus in the soil of the Bukhara region has decreased by 0.35% over the past 25 years. How long will it take to restore it? Imagine if 30 tons of local organic fertilizer are applied to a hectare of land in manure turnover every three years, the amount of humus in the soil will increase by 0.1% in 10 years. To increase the amount of humus in the soil, it is necessary to apply local fertilizer to the land. Let's look at the measures taken by foreign countries in this regard. For example, in France, 23 tons of organic fertilizers are applied per hectare of cultivated land annually, in England 26 tons, and in Germany 26.5 tons, while in the Netherlands, which is considered a model of world agriculture, 78-80 tons of

fertilizers are applied per hectare of land annually. In our cultivated lands, the amount of mineral fertilizers is increasing year by year, as a result of which the porosity of the soil composition of the cultivated lands is decreasing and its hardness is increasing. Experiments have shown that after irrigation of row-planted cotton crops during the irrigation period, due to the low content of organic matter and humus in the soil, clods are formed. [4]

Figure 1. Crop area of the "Donyor Shukur" farm, Shafirkan district, Bukhara region.

Such conditions are present in almost all cultivated areas of the Bukhara region, as they are formed due to the increase in the salinity level of cultivated areas, the decrease in the amount of humus and organic fertilizers in the soil, as a result of which the moisture content of the cultivated areas decreases, which leads to an increase in water consumption during irrigation and the need for shallow cultivation 3-4 times after each irrigation, which has a negative impact on economic efficiency, as a result of experiments and research. As a result of cultivation by cultivators, large lumpy wedges are formed, requiring additional cultivation, and the entry of heavy machinery into the cultivated areas during one irrigation period increases the density of the cultivated areas and reduces their porosity (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The process of shallow tillage between cotton rows

It was found that these shortcomings can be eliminated and water consumption during irrigation reduced by creating a device that applies local fertilizer between cotton rows to maintain moisture. The use of local fertilizers in the cultivation of high yields of agricultural crops is important in increasing their productivity. The yield obtained in agriculture is grown due to the absorption and assimilation of various substances in the soil. There is a special demand for food products exported to the world market to be biologically pure products. In order to produce biologically pure products in world markets, attention should be paid to the agrotechnics of the plant being grown.

In particular, during the vegetation period of the plant, chemical preparations and mineral fertilizers should be used as little as possible.

Currently, local fertilizers, namely animal waste (manure), compost (mixtures of plant stems and various wastes), are widely used as the main plant nutrients. Solid local fertilizers are prepared in two ways: directly (farm-field) and in the form of accumulation (farm-storage-field). In this case, local fertilizers are mainly loaded onto vehicles from livestock farmers' storage facilities and transported to a prepared storage facility at the beginning of the field. Then they are stored there until the planting period and are applied to the soil when necessary. In non-saline areas, solid and liquid local fertilizers are applied to the surface of the soil before plowing, and then plowing is organized. In saline areas, it is advisable to apply them during soil cultivation after the salt has been washed off.

Figure 3. General view of a device for applying local fertilizer between cotton rows

In the structural scheme of the device for applying local fertilizer to the cotton rows, after the organic fertilizer particles fall from the fertilizer discharge slot of the bunker, they begin to move freely in the air with an initial velocity V_0 , which is directed vertically from top to bottom, and after a while they fall into the fertilizer transfer chute, which transfers fertilizer. We will study the free movement of fertilizer particles in the air. In the air, they move vertically along the Z axis. The number of rotations of the agitator. This parameter was determined due to the need to ensure that large pieces of fertilizer placed in the machine bunker are crushed under the action of the blades of the agitator.

Figure 4. Graphs of the relationships a) V_x (a) and b) $X(b)$.

It moves from top to bottom. In this case, the force of gravity $G = m_b g$ and the air resistance force R_x act on them. Under the influence of these forces, we formulate a differential equation

for the motion of a piece of fertilizer along the Z axis. We consider the air resistance force R_x to be proportional to the first level of power of the speed.

$$R_x = kmbZ \quad (1)$$

Taking into account (1), equation (2) takes the following form:

$$Z = g - kZ \quad (2)$$

We replace Z in this expression with dZ / dt , giving the following form.

$$\frac{dZ}{g - kZ} = dt \quad (3)$$

The integral of this expression takes the form.

$$\int \frac{dZ}{g - kZ} = \int dt - \frac{1}{k} \ln(g - kZ) = t + C_3 \quad (4)$$

here C_3 – constant of integration.

From the condition of the problem, if $t=0$, then $Z = V_0$. If we putting these into (4)

$$C_3 = -\frac{1}{k} \ln(g - kV_0) \quad (5)$$

If we substitute the value of C_3 according to (4) into (5), the following equation is obtained.

$$\frac{1}{k} \ln \frac{(g - kV_0)}{(g - kZ)} = t \quad (6)$$

This equation describes the movement of fertilizer particles after they fall through the fertilizer discharge slot of the hopper. With the arguments $g=9,81 \text{ m/s}^2$, $k=0,1 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $V_0=0,51 \text{ m/s}$, a graph of the change of (Z) as a function of (t) is constructed. By placing the vertical distance of

10 sm from the fertilizer discharge slot of the hopper to the fertilizer feed chute on the ordinate axis, we determine the value of the free movement time of the fertilizer particle $t=0.10 \text{ s}$

By expressing the time (t) of the movement of the fertilizer particle, we determine the velocity V_T at which the manure particle falls into the fertilizer transfer tube.

Analysis of research results. The device works as follows; the device is attached to the tractor via a hitch and the bunker of the device is filled with organic fertilizer. When the tractor moves forward along the rows, the device is lowered to the working position via the tractor suspension and the milling blades placed inside the bunker via a chain transmission grind the organic fertilizer and the angle of inclination of the bunker walls is greater than the angle of friction of the organic fertilizer on them, which ensures the free sliding of the manure particles along them. Based on the results of the research, it was concluded that in order for the fertilizer pieces to be evenly distributed in the furrow formed after falling from the trough, not to jump in it and not to move to one side or the other, it is necessary to correctly select the angle of the trough relative to the horizon of 40° , and for the machine's disheveler to completely crush large pieces of fertilizer, its number of revolutions should be at least 27 r/min, the length of its blades should be at least 10 sm,

Figure 5. Testing process of the inter-row localized fertilizer application machine.

and the longitudinal distance between them should be no more than 10 sm. Figure 4 shows the testing process of the machine for applying localized fertilizer between crop rows.

Conclusion: Based on the analytical and theoretical studies conducted, we found that the method of evenly applying organic fertilizers between 60 sm cotton rows in the area where their roots develop is effective, and as a result, it is economically efficient to maintain moisture at 30% and not to require additional tillage techniques. It is of great importance in increasing the productivity of cultivated areas and creating a fertile soil layer

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